

Direct electrochemical synthesis of organotin and lead compounds with pyridine-2-thione ligand

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The electrochemical oxidation of anodic metals Sn and Pb in binary system consisting of acetonitrile (MeCN) and dimethylformamide (DMF) as solvent and pyridine-2-thione (pyt-H) as solute, gives complexes [Sn(pyt)₂] and [Pb(pyt)₂], respectively. Pyridine-2-thione (pyt-H) acts as a bidentate ligand and that the geometry of the complexes is tetrahedral.

The direct electrochemical synthesis of tin and lead compounds with hetrocyclic donor ligands, has been the subject of great interest due to their wide ranging applications : especially polymerization catalyst, antiseptic action, preservatives and stabilisers etc. in various industries^{1,2}. In this synthesis, the metallic foils of tin and lead act as anode *in situ*. Since, pure metallic foils are directly used and no extraneous oxidation or reducing agents are added, more pure compounds can be expected through this technique using sacrificial metal anodes. Hence, this technique may be useful for the synthesis of organometallic compounds because it provides shorter and more economical route.

This communication presents the synthesis of [M(pyt)₂], where M = Sn, Pb, by direct electrochemical oxidation of metal in a solution of pyridine-2-thione (pyt-H) in mixed solvent of acetonitrile and DMF.

Results and Discussion

Experimental conditions for electrochemical synthesis are presented in Table 1. The isolated compounds could not remain stable for long time as they were converted into polymers. The electrochemical oxidation of tin and lead in nonaqueous solution of pyridine-2-thione is an efficient and simple route to the appropriate [M(pyt)₂] compounds. The electrochemical efficiency (E_f) was close to 0.5 mol F⁻¹ and the cell reaction of this electrochemical synthesis is as follows :

where L⁻ is monoanionic form of pyt-H.

The compounds (pale brown) were found soluble in most of the organic solvents. The 3160 cm⁻¹ (NH) ligand

band is absent in the IR spectra of the complexes. The complexes show bands at 670–708 (C–S) and 1648–1655 cm⁻¹ (C=N). The changes in the position of $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ bands of the complexes indicate that the ligand is complexed through sulfur and nitrogen^{3,4} atoms. This establishes the bidentate nature of the ligand as monoanionic form. ¹H NMR spectra show that the signal at 13.43 (br s, NH) of the free pyt-H is absent in the metal complexes, suggesting deprotonation in the ligand. Thus, ligand behaves as thionato form in the present complexes. Besides, the complexes exhibit four distinct and widely separated signals of equal intensity assignable to the four non-equivalent hydrogen of pyt-H ligands^{4,5}. The ¹³C NMR spectrum (vide Experimental) explains the reduction of the C=S bond order⁶. This fact also support the evidence of thionato form of the ligand which is coordinated to the metal complex.

Based on the above findings, a tetrahedral structure has been suggested for the complexes.

Table 1 Experimental condition for electrochemical synthesis along with the colour, decomposition temperature of the complexes*

Compd	Amt. of ligand g	Current (A)/ (Voltage, V) V	Time h	Metal dissolved g	Decomp. temp °C
[Sn(pyt) ₂] ^a	0.614	0.2 (28)	3	0.158	140
[Pb(pyt) ₂] ^b	0.535	0.05 (30)	5	0.386	150

*Yields : ^a60%, ^b55%.

Experimental

Acetonitrile, DMF, pyridine-2-thione (pyt-H) (all A.R.) were used as such. Tin and lead (Ega Chemic) were used as plates (ca 1.8 × 1.2 cm).

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Note

Synthesis : The electrochemical method used in the synthesis of the compounds was similar to that described earlier^{2,7}. The cell was a 100 cm³ tall form beaker. The metal anode (Sn and Pb) was suspended from platinum wire and second Pt-wire was used as cathode. The ligand was dissolved in acetonitrile and tetramethylammonium perchlorate (0.1 g) was added as supporting electrolyte. The electric power was supplied by a dc power. The electrolyte contained acetonitrile (20 ml) and DMF (5 ml). The reaction conditions are given in Table 1. During electrolysis, dry nitrogen was bubbled through the solution to provide an inert atmosphere. H₂ (g) was evolved at the cathode and the solution became warm. After electrolysis the solid product was scrapped from the surface of the anode, washed with acetonitrile followed by methanol and dried. The purity of compounds were checked by TLC : [Sn(pyt)₂] ¹H NMR δ 7.63(d), 6.75(t), 7.42(m), 7.28(d), ¹³C NMR δ 119.8, 130.5, 139.0, 146.0, 175.8; [Pb(pyt)₂] ¹H NMR δ 7.81(d), 6.77(t), 7.35(m), 7.26(d), ¹³C NMR δ 116.2, 124.9, 138.5, 146.8, 173.2.

Sulfur was estimated by the usual gravimetric method and nitrogen by Kjeldhal method. The composition of the compounds was further confirmed by satisfactory C, H, N analysis. IR spectra was obtained in KBr pellets and NMR (¹H, ¹³C) spectra in DMSO-d₆ using TMS as an internal standard.

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